

Resource Sheet

Research Software and NRENs in Asia

Episode 3: Role of Libraries in Research Support for Scientific Software

Session information

Webpage	https://rse-asia.github.io/RSE_Asia/event/2026-05-12_ep-3-library/
Date	12 May 2026
Time	07:00 - 08:00 am UTC
Facilitators	Saranjeet Kaur Bhogal Jyoti Bhogal
Guest	Victoria Caplan

Important links

- [Registration link - Episode 4: Open Science, Research Infrastructure, and Collaboration](#)
- [RSE Asia survey link](#)
- RSE Asia [Community Membership form](#)

Resources and info from us

RSE Asia

- Website: https://rse-asia.github.io/RSE_Asia/
- For the latest news, events, activities, and opportunities, follow us on our [Linkedln page](#)
- To join the RSE Asia community, please fill out our short [Community Membership Form](#)

Shared resources from the session

- Organisations
 - [Hong Kong University of Science and Technology \(HKUST\)](#)
 - HKUST library website - <https://library.hkust.edu.hk/>
 - [HKSUT SPD](#) - for the institutional library
 - HKUST Digital Humanities - <https://digitalhumanities.hkust.edu.hk/>
- Training, certifications, books
 - 5 laws of library science:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Five_laws_of_library_science: Book by S. R. Ranganathan
 - A science fiction book by author Lois McMaster Bujold
 - Quote: “The questions don't change, but the answers do”
- News:
 - [Canvas issue about a cyber attack on libraries in schools and universities](#)
- Examples of Reference management system
 - [BibTex](#)
 - [Zotero](#)
 - [EndNote](#)
- Research databases and sources
 - [Google Scholar](#)
 - [SciVal](#)
 - [PubMed](#)
- LLM-based tools for research literature
 - [Undermind](#)
 - [Elicit](#)
 - [Consensus](#)
- Interactive digital teaching tools
 - [Menti](#)
 - [Lucid](#)
- Library coding
 - [MARC coding](#)
 - [Dublin Core](#)
- Academic databases
 - [Scopus](#)
 - [Web of Science](#)
 - [Semantic Web](#)

Upcoming events from around the world

- [Research Software Asia Australia 2026 \(RSAA26\)](#), 25-28 August 2026, online - [Call for Presentations is now open](#)